

Monorepos for Research Software Projects

Geoffrey Lentner

Rosen Center for Advanced Computing

Purdue University

West Lafayette, Indiana

0000-0001-9314-0683

Abstract—Full-stack research software projects typically include several components and have many dependencies. New projects benefit from co-development of these components within a well-structured monolith. While this is preferred, over time this can become a burden to deploy in different contexts and environments. What we would like is to independently deploy components to reduce size and complexity. Maintaining separate packages however allows for developmental drift and other problems. So called *monorepos* allow for the best of both approaches, but not without its own difficulties. There is almost no formal treatment in the literature of this particular dilemma however. The technology industry has started using monorepos to solve similar challenges, but perhaps in the academic context we should be cautious to not simply replicate industry practices. This short paper merely propositions the research software engineering (RSE) community into a discussion of the positives and negatives in structuring projects as monorepos of discrete packages.

Index Terms—software, development, version control, monorepo

I. INTRODUCTION

Almost as soon as the world invented the modern notion of computing, so too were programming practices. From the beginning, software engineering has continually evolved as a discipline, with strongly held opinions on design, structure, management, and tools. With each generation we reinvent old ideas and reimagine what is appropriate or best practice. This differs by field, it differs by community, it differs between programming languages, and it differs between present day *industry* and *academia*.

In the modern age, some practices have largely congealed around essential project structures, version control systems, and other elements, particularly in the context of the open-source community. In what is likely an outgrowth of the original UNIX legacy regarding software programs (and libraries) ‘doing one thing,’ alongside the proliferation of online package repositories and developer tooling in modern languages, it is now common practice to create small, narrowly scoped packages. For application projects however it is often ambiguous to delineate the boundaries where small packages can or should be factored out.

More recently, large technology companies have begun to push the boundaries in this domain by breaking up their projects (i.e., applications) into a globally distributed microservice architecture. For some of the very largest technology

companies, perhaps paradoxically, they manage these within a single, so called ‘monorepo’.

Here we want to identify the motivations, benefits, issues, and management methods that surround such choices. While there are lots of opinions on offer online within tech articles and blog posts on the topic of monorepos in the industrial context [1]–[5], there is no strong literature discussing the topic and its practice on a more modest scale, and certainly not within the arena of research software engineering.

The goal of this short paper is to plainly present a common scenario in an RSE context and walk through the progression towards a new project structure, with its merits and challenges exposed.

II. USE-CASE

A common use-case in research computing is to connect a community of professional researchers and possibly some public facing network of amateurs by building an end-to-end system behind a front-end (sometimes called a *science gateway*) that automates some collection of regularized computational tasks and their data with users. This typically includes some public cloud or academic cluster of machines running tasks, driven by an orchestration component, on top of a data repository (an RDBMS or similar), driven by a RESTful API, all presented by a front-end web interface with user login, administration, views, and workflows. The author is the lead RSE on one such project doing just that within the astronomy community.

This project is motivated by the need to cope with the imminent deluge of new candidate supernovae discovered by the up-and-coming LSST survey (lsst.org), taking the number of nightly observed novel events up by several orders of magnitude (from some 10s to now 10k). There are not enough professional or amateur astronomers worldwide to follow-up on all of them, and the most attractive objects would otherwise be observed unnecessarily often. The solution is to implement a data-driven observing strategy that optimizes science objectives across a global community of participants.

Thus, we have built an intelligent recommendation system (called REFITT, refitt.org); a large, coherent system of services, workloads, and tools that falls into the genre of RSE projects described above.

The project is an end-to-end system that connects multiple external data streams to a continuous high-performance computing pipeline which produces time-series forecasts of candi-

date events. An observation planning system feeds these results into a recommendation system that coordinates a world-wide network of participating astronomers and telescope facilities based on individual capability, capacity, and priority. All of this to produce a globally optimal cycle of data collection that meets the scientific objectives of the astronomy community.

There is not space to describe this project in detail. As described in these general terms however, it represents a sufficient proxy for similar such projects in many domains.

III. DISCUSSION

This project like many is built almost entirely in the Python programming language; as the data science and data engineering tasks, the automation, and web-facing are all well provided for. From the very beginning, all these components were identified and understood. Developing them together within a single monolithic Python package is entirely practical and altogether sensible. These components all share the same underlying runtime, core functions (e.g., configuration, logging, etc.), and history. All other things being equal, this is generally preferable.

Because they exist within the same package structure, all components are always deployed together, regardless of the potentially lesser role of a given deployment environment (HPC pipeline vs. app server vs. end-user PC). While taking up space, this does not represent an existential risk on modern machines. In our case however, we always intended to expose the API to end-users who wished to automate their workflow and bypass the web front-end. To facilitate this, we developed a simplified command-line interface that handles the token-based authentication, endpoint structure, parameters, etc. Users simply invoke the client tool, and everything is taken care of, including rich data formatting options.

The problem is that now the users are asked to install the full system in order to use the client tool, because they share the same core modules and domain model. The solution is to break up the package into multiple independently deployable sub-packages so that the thin client does not depend on the other heavy data science dependencies; i.e., why install *TensorFlow* to simply query an API? The downside to this however (assuming separate version control repositories for each) is the loss of shared history, accidental developmental drift between the sub-packages, duplicate commits in some scenarios, and other issues.

Instead, keeping these individual package source trees within the same version control repository in many ways provides for the best of both approaches. It maintains the shared history, it allows for atomic commits involving multiple components, improved testing strategies, streamlined CI/CD (continuous integration and continuous deployment), simplified refactoring and debugging, and unified versioning. All of this is conserved while allowing for independently deployable components of the system.

This is not without new challenges. While this works well for small teams, for larger teams this introduces problems with managing the project, including branching and merging

strategies, ownership and permissions, among other aspects of version control systems. As well, additional tools may be necessary to cope with the non-traditional project structure. Code editors (IDEs) also tend not to understand this structure.

IV. CONCLUSION

While only barely touching the surface of this topic, hopefully this short paper sufficiently compels the community into a discussion of alternate approaches to these sorts of RSE projects. The included appendix suggests a possible source repository structure.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Whitney, "Notes on the Monorepo Pattern," DEV Community (Online), Dec 2022. https://dev.to/david_whitney/notes-on-the-monorepo-pattern-5egc (Retrieved on May 2022).
- [2] T. Fernandez, "What is monorepo? (and should you use it?)," Semaphore (Online), July 2022. <https://semaphoreci.com/blog/what-is-monorepo> (Retrieved on May 2022).
- [3] D. Hipschman, "Our Python Monorepo," Open House. Medium (Online), June 2020. <https://medium.com/opendoor-labs/our-python-monorepo-d34028f2b6fa> (Retrieved on May 2022).
- [4] N. Brousse, "The issue of monorepo and polyrepo in large enterprises," 3rd International Companion Conference, April 2019. pp 1-4. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3328433.3328435>.
- [5] G. Brito, R. Terra, and M. Valente, "Monorepos: a multivocal literature review," arXiv preprint. 2018. arXiv:1810.09477

APPENDIX A

An example project structure is included for consideration [3]. The `lib/` folder contains sub-packages that may depend on each other but cannot depend on anything in `project/`. Components in `project/` cannot depend on each other and can only depend on components in `lib/`. The file tree is only expanded for one sub-package to illustrate the structure within. Not all elements of the repository are included for the sake of simplicity (e.g., README or LICENSE files). The outer `pyproject.toml` represents a virtual package and overall project metadata.

```

refitt/
|-- docs/...
|-- py/
|   |-- lib/
|       |-- refitt-core/
|       |   |-- pyproject.toml
|       |   |-- src/
|       |   |-- refitt/
|       |   |-- core/
|       |   |-- ...
|       |-- tests/
|       |-- ...
|   |-- refitt-data/
|-- project/
|   |-- refitt-admin/
|   |-- refitt-api/
|   |-- refitt-client/
|   |-- refitt-pipeline/
|   |-- refitt-web/
|-- pyproject.toml
`-- tests/...

```